

Comparative Study of Monopolar versus Bipolar Transurethral Resection of Benign Prostate for Safety and Complications (Related to Technique) under Regional Anaesthesia

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Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 25-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH) is one of the most common causes of lower urinary tract symptoms in elderly men. Management of BPH includes conservative or watchful waiting, medical therapies, and surgical interventions. Monopolar transurethral resection of prostate (TURP) is considered as the surgical gold standard for BPH. TURP syndrome is a rare but most dreaded complication of TURP. The aim of the present study is to compare the safety profile of these two techniques of TURP- monopolar and bipolar in terms of incidence of TUR syndrome and other complications.

Study Design: Prospective observational comparative study.

Method: 23 patients in each group, total 46 patients, divided into two groups - Group M (monopolar TURP) and Group B (bipolar TURP) who underwent TURP under regional anaesthesia. Duration of surgery, blood loss, intraop complications like TUR syndrome, post-op serum electrolyte and haemoglobin level (immediate post op & 24 hrs after surgery) were analyzed.

Results: The change in hemoglobin values from pre-op to immediate postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group(0.81+/-0.16) compared to the bipolar group(0.40+/-0.17) with a p value<0.001. Also, the change in serum sodium values was significantly more in the monopolar group(4.13+/- 1.14) compared to the bipolar group(0.83+/-0.89) with a p value<0.001. No case of TUR syndrome was recorded. The duration of surgery (62.04+/-4.07 minutes) and amount of irrigation fluid used (4.63+/-0.48 liters) was significantly lesser in the bipolar group as compared to monopolar group (66.39+/-3.38 minutes) & (5.08+/-0.45 liters) respectively p value < 0.001.

Conclusion: We conclude that Bipolar TURP is better in terms of safety and complication rates compared to monopolar TURP.

Keywords: TURP Syndrome, Regional Anaesthesia, Monopolar & Bipolar Resectoscope, Biochemical Marker.

Key Messages: Two techniques of TURP – Monopolar and Bipolar.

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Introduction

Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia(BPH) is one of the most common causes of lower urinary tract symptoms(LUTS) in elderly men.[1] Management of BPH includes conservative or watchful waiting, medical therapies and surgical interventions.[2] Surgical options available for BPH include minimally invasive therapies, transurethral resection of the prostate(TURP), transurethral incision of the prostate(TUIP), photo selective vaporization of the prostate(PVP), holmium laser resection of the prostate(HoLRP) and prostatectomy.[3] Monopolar TURP is considered as the surgical gold standard for BPH.[4]

Transurethral resection(TUR) syndrome is a rare but most dreaded complication of TURP. Concerns about TUR syndrome associated with monopolar TURP led to the introduction of bipolar TURP. Bipolar diathermy allows the use of 0.9% sodium chloride also called as isotonic saline as irrigation fluid. Isotonic saline is more physiological compared to 1.5% glycine decreases the risk of TUR syndrome.[5] Isotonic saline conducts electricity and cannot be used in monopolar TURP. Another advantage of bipolar TURP is its improved hemostatic ability resulting in better intraoperative visualization. Other complications associated with

TURP are hypothermia, blood loss, clot retention, bladder perforation, urethral strictures, urinary tract infections and urinary retention. [6,7] For TURP regional anesthesia is preferred for monitoring the patient's mental status intraoperatively and early recognition of signs and symptoms of TUR syndrome. The incidence of deep vein thrombosis is decreased, and the amount of operative blood loss is reduced with regional anesthesia compared with general anesthesia. Another added advantage of regional anesthesia is decreased requirement of analgesics in the immediate postoperative period. Both monopolar and bipolar TURP are comparable in terms of efficacy. The aim of the present study is to compare the safety profile of these two techniques of TURP in terms of incidence of TUR syndrome and other complications while using different irrigation fluids - 1.5% glycine for monopolar TURP and 0.9% normal saline for bipolar TURP respectively performed under regional anesthesia.

Aims and Objectives

- 1. Primary objective:** To study the incidence of TUR Syndrome in Monopolar versus Bipolar transurethral resection of prostate
- 2. Secondary objective:** To study other complications associated with the two techniques of TURP under regional anesthesia.

Material and Methods

The study began after obtaining permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee. All patients were explained the purpose and rationale of the study as well as their role as participants in the study. Written informed consent was obtained from all the patients.

Study Design: Prospective Observational Comparative study.

Study Setting: Uro surgery Operation theatre and ward.

Study Period: 1 year.

Sample Size Calculation: Sample size was calculated with the help of article "Bipolar versus monopolar transurethral prostate resection: Comparison of hemodynamic and biochemical changes' Egyptian Journal of Anaesthesia (2014) 30, 47-52" taking into consideration study parameters - 'duration of surgery, change in hemoglobin and serum sodium levels' with the help of Difference in 'Mean of two samples' method at 80% power and 95% confidence interval. The calculated sample size was 23 respectively for each group.

Thus, the total sample size was 46, 23 participants in each group.

Study Population: This prospective study was conducted in 46 patients. All patients scheduled for elective surgery were screened and enrolled on the basis of the study selection criteria. Every enrolled patient was briefed about the purpose of the study and their written, valid, informed consent was taken.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients with following criteria were selected for this study:

- Age >50 years.
- Patients with ASA grade 1 & 2.
- Patients of BPH with prostate gland weighing >40 grams.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with following criteria were excluded from study:

- Age >85 years.
- Patients with ASA grade 3&4.
- Previous h/o prostate, bladder neck or urethral surgery.
- Prostate carcinoma.
- Patients who will receive general anesthesia for BPH resection.
- Patients with deranged coagulation profile.
- Patients on aspirin treatment.

Study Procedure: 46 patients with BPH fulfilling all inclusion criteria and not complying to any exclusion criteria, were enrolled, and equally divided into two groups - Group M (monopolar TURP) in which surgery was performed by monopolar resectoscope and Group B (bipolar TURP) in which surgery was performed by bipolar technique of resection for BPH.

Either Spinal or Combined Epidural and Spinal Anaesthesia was chosen as the technique of anesthesia. Under all aseptic precautions, spinal anesthesia was given using 23 G Quincke's spinal needle. The drug used was 3.5ml of 0.5% heavy bupivacaine & 60 mcg buprenorphine. For epidural, the epidural catheter was inserted in L1 & L2 space using the loss of resistance to air technique for epidural space identification. The test dose of 3ml of lignocaine 2% was used for epidural followed by infusion of 0.25% sensorcaine @ 5ml/hour started 1hour after test dose & continued until the end of the surgery.

Glycine was used as irrigation fluid for patients undergoing Monopolar TURP and amount of glycine utilized for irrigation was calculated in liters. For patients undergoing Bipolar TURP, irrigation used was normal saline, the amount of which was also calculated in liters. Duration of anesthesia & duration of surgery was noted in minutes.

Parameters to be assessed

1. Duration of anesthesia - from the time of T10 sensory block to regression to L1 level.
2. Duration of surgery - from the insertion of resectoscope to end of the procedure.
3. Blood loss - assessed as a drop in hemoglobin level.
4. The weight of the excised prostate gland.
5. Intra-op complications:
 - TUR syndrome
 - Perforation of bladder
 - Hypothermia
 - Bleeding
 - Intra-op bladder spasm
 - Any other medical complications - cardiac, respiratory, CNS and any other.
6. Post-op serum electrolytes (sodium, potassium, chloride) - immediate post op & 24 hours after surgery.
7. Hemoglobin levels - immediate post op & 24 hours after surgery.
8. Post-op complications:
 - TUR syndrome

- Post op nausea vomiting (PONV) - mild/moderate/severe

Statistical Analysis: The data was collected and compiled using Epi Info 7.2. The qualitative variables were expressed in terms of proportions and the difference between the two proportions was tested by Chi-square or Fisher exact test. The quantitative variables were either categorized and expressed in percentages or in terms of mean and standard deviation. The correlation between the two continuous variables was assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. The difference between two means was tested by t-test. All analysis were two-tailed, and the significance level was set at 0.05.

Results

Table 1 presents the demography of patients participated in the study. No significant differences were observed in terms of mean age, weight of the patients between the two study groups. The mean age of the patients in the monopolar group was 67.48+/-5.21 yrs and in bipolar group, it was 67.09+/-4.75 yrs. It was comparable in both the groups with p-value 0.7914. The mean weight of the patients in the monopolar group was 66.26+/-3.98 kgs and in bipolar group, it was 68.17+/-3.18 kgs. It was comparable in both the groups with p-value 0.4352

Table 1: Patients demographics

Variable	Group M		Group B		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age (in years)	67.48	5.21	67.09	4.75	0.7914
Weight (in kg)	66.27	3.98	68.17	3.88	0.4352

Table 2: Distribution study groups based on duration of surgery

Duration of Surgery	Group M		Group B		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
	66.39	3.38	62.04	4.07	0.0003* b

b-unpaired test, *significant

Figure 1: Distribution of study subjects based on duration of surgery

From Table 2 and figure 1, it was observed that the mean duration of surgery in the monopolar group was 66.39+/-3.38 minutes and in bipolar group, it

was 62.04+/-4.07 minutes. It was significantly more in the monopolar group than bipolar group with a p-value of 0.0003

Table 3: Distribution of study subjects based on the amount of irrigant used

Amount of irrigant used	Group M		Group B		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
	5.08	0.45	4.63	0.48	0.0020* ^b
b-unpaired t-test applied, *significant					

Figure 2: Distribution of study subjects based on the amount of irrigant used

From table 3 and figure 2, it was observed that, the amount of glycine used in monopolar TURP was 5.08+/-0.45 liters. This was significantly more than

the amount of isotonic saline used as the irrigant in bipolar TURP i.e., 4.63+/-0.48 liters. P value was 0.0020.

Table 4: Comparison of change in parameters from pre-op to immediate postoperatively between two groups

Parameters	Group M		Group B		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Change in Hb	0.81	0.16	0.40	0.17	<0.001*
Change in Na	4.13	1.14	0.83	0.89	<0.001*
Change in K	0.07	0.07	0.10	0.09	0.3555
*Significant					

Figure 3: Comparison of change in parameters from pre-op to immediate postoperatively between two groups

From table 4 and figure3 it was observed that, the change in hemoglobin values from pre-op to

immediate postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group(0.81+/-0.16) compared to the bipolar group(0.40+/-0.17) with a p

value<0.001. Also, The change in serum sodium values from

1.14) compared to the bipolar group(0.83+/-0.89) with a p value<0.001. There was no significant change in serum potassium levels.

pre-op to immediate postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group(4.13+/-

Table 5: Comparison of change in parameters from pre-op to 24 hours postoperatively between two groups

Parameters	Group M		Group B		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Change in Hb	0.89	0.27	0.42	0.19	<0.001*
Change in Na	3.74	1.18	0.96	1.22	<0.001*
Change in K	0.09	0.05	0.11	0.08	0.2103

*Significant

Figure 4: Comparison of change in parameters from pre-op to 24 hours postoperatively between two groups

From table 5 and figure 4,it was observed that, the change in hemoglobin values from pre-op to 24 hours postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group(0.89+/-0.27) compared to the bipolar group(0.42+/-0.19) with a p value<0.001.

Also, The change in serum sodium values from pre-op to 24 hours postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group(3.74+/-1.18) compared to the bipolar group(0.96+/-1.12) with a p value<0.001. There was no significant change in serum potassium levels.

Table 6: Correlation of duration of surgery with the difference in pre to postoperative values of various parameters

Change in parameters	Group M		Group B		Total R	P value
	r	P value	R	P value		
Difference Hb immediate	-0.043	0.847	-0.040	0.857	0.380	0.009*
Difference Hb 24 hour	0.122	0.580	0.046	0.855	0.415	0.004*
Difference Na immediate	0.033	0.880	0.732	0.000	0.598	0.000*
Difference Na 24 hour	0.130	0.555	0.675	0.000	0.630	0.000*
Difference K immediate	-0.130	0.555	0.115	0.601	-0.056	0.714
Difference K 24 hour	-0.192	0.380	0.149	0.498	-0.074	0.626
Difference tem- perature immediate	0.343	0.110	-0.020	0.926	0.189	0.208

*Significant

From table 6, it was observed that, a positive correlation has been found between the duration of sug

ery and change in hemoglobin and serum sodium levels both immediate and 24 hours postoperative.

Table 7: Distribution of study subjects based on intra and postoperative complications

Complications	Group M		Group B		P value
	Number	%	Number	%	
TUR syndrome	0	0	0	0	
PONV					
Nil	11	47.83	11	47.83	0.9041 ^a
Mild	3	13.04	4	17.39	
Moderate	9	39.13	8	34.78	
Bleeding	1	4.35	0	0	1.000 ^a
VAS score (Pain)	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	P value
	2.65	1.15	2.52	1.12	0.6994 ^b

a-Chi square test or Fisher's exact test applied; b-unpaired t-test applied

There was a significant change in hemoglobin and serum sodium levels postoperatively in the monopolar group, but no case of TUR syndrome was reported. Postoperative bleeding occurred in one case of monopolar TURP. No other complications of TURP were recorded.

Discussion

Despite great availability and advancement in treatment options for BPH, TURP is still considered as the gold standard surgical procedure for BPH. Monopolar TURP has been used for a very long time with considerable success, but concerns about TUR syndrome led to the introduction of bipolar TURP. Besides the improved hemostatic ability of bipolar diathermy, the main advantage of bipolar TURP is the use of 0.9% isotonic saline as irrigation fluid. Isotonic saline is a more physiological solution compared to 1.5% glycine used in monopolar TURP. Glycine is a hypotonic solution, a large amount of which if absorbed in systemic circulation can lead to TUR syndrome.

In our study, we are comparing the complications primarily TUR syndrome and thus the safety of monopolar versus bipolar TURP done in our institute. A total of 46 patients were enrolled in this prospective observational study. 23 patients in each group. The patients were observed till 24 hours after surgery.

The mean age of the patients in the monopolar group was 67.48 \pm 5.21 yrs and in bipolar group, it was 67.09 \pm 4.75 yrs. It was comparable in both the groups with p-value 0.7914. In a study conducted by T Jagadeeswar in 2015, the mean age of study subjects was 69.6 \pm 7.6 yrs in the monopolar group and 68.4 \pm 7.8 yrs in the bipolar group, similar to our study.[8] Also, it was similar to a study conducted by Carlos E. Méndez-Probst et al in 2011 where it was 67 \pm 7 yrs in the monopolar group and 68 \pm 7 yrs in the bipolar group.[9] The incidence of BPH increases with increasing age.

The mean weight of the patients in the monopolar group was 67.26 \pm 3.98 kgs and in bipolar group, it

was 68.17 \pm 3.18 kgs. It was comparable in both the groups with p-value 0.4352.

The patients included in our study were classified as ASA 1 & 2 according to American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) classification. The technique of anesthesia chosen for our study was regional anesthesia. All the cases were done under spinal anesthesia. Regional anesthesia allows early recognition of signs and symptoms of fluid overload and TUR syndrome. Accidental bladder perforation can also be recognized easily if the spinal level is limited to T10. The technique of anesthesia was standardized for all study subjects. Under all aseptic precautions, spinal anesthesia was given using 23 G Quincke's spinal needle. The drug used was 3.5ml of 0.5% heavy bupivacaine & 60 mcg buprenorphine. The anesthesia technique was not standardized in a study by Henry S.S. Ho et al where 4 patients in monopolar and 3 patients in the bipolar group were given general anesthesia depending on patient factors.[10] In our study, only ASA 1 & 2 patients fit for regional anesthesia were included.

Duration of anesthesia defined as the time from achieving T10 sensory block after spinal anesthesia to regression of sensory block to L1 level was noted in minutes for both the groups. The mean duration of anesthesia in the monopolar group was 122.96 \pm 5.59 minutes and in bipolar group, it was 123.91 \pm 5.46 minutes. It was comparable in both the groups with a p-value of 0.5602 probably due to the standardization of anesthesia technique and similar demographic profile of study subjects in both the groups.

The mean duration of surgery in the monopolar group was 66.39 \pm 3.38 minutes and in bipolar group, it was 62.04 \pm 4.07 minutes. It was significantly more in the monopolar group with a p-value of 0.0003, owing to better hemostatic ability and thus improved the field of vision in bipolar TURP. This is similar to study by Erturhan S et al, Fagerstrom et al.[11,12] Significantly longer resection times with bipolar group have been reported by Michielsen et al, Mohamed Hafez El Saied Hafez et al, and Huang et al.[13,14,15]

Marco de Sio et al, T.Jagadeeswar et al, Henry S.S. Ho et al found no significant difference in the duration of the resection between the two groups.[5,8,10]

The mean weight of the resected gland in the monopolar group was 18.09 \pm 2.63 gms and in bipolar group, it was 17.78 \pm 2.41 gms. It was comparable in both the groups with p-value 0.6843. Marco de Sio et al, T. Jagadeeswar et al and Henry S.S. Ho et al also didn't find a significant difference in weight of resected gland in both the groups. [5,8,10]

The irrigation fluid used for monopolar TURP was 1.5% glycine and for bipolar TURP, it was 0.9% sodium chloride. The amount of glycine used in monopolar TURP (5.08 \pm 0.45 liters) was significantly more than the amount of isotonic saline used in bipolar TURP (4.63 \pm 0.48 liters) with a P-value of 0.0020. Erturhan et al also found the reduced use of irrigation fluids in the bipolar group compared to monopolar.[11] The reduced irrigation fluid used in bipolar TURP decreases the risk of TUR syndrome. In a study done by Mohamed Hafez El Saied Hafez et al, the total volume of glycine used in the monopolar group was less than the total volume of saline used in the bipolar group probably due to the longer resection time in the bipolar group.[14]

Our study results showed a significant drop in hemoglobin in the monopolar group compared to the bipolar group both immediate postoperatively and 24 hours postoperatively. The change in hemoglobin values from pre-op to immediate postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group (0.81 \pm 0.16) compared to the bipolar group (0.40 \pm 0.17) with a p value<0.001. Also, the change in hemoglobin values from pre-op to 24 hours postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group (0.89 \pm 0.27) compared to the bipolar group (0.42 \pm 0.19) with a p value<0.001. Fagerstrom et al, Mohamed Hafez El Saied Hafez et al and Piyush Singhanian et al also found a similar significant drop in hemoglobin in the monopolar group in their study although blood transfusion was not required in any of the patients.[12,14,16] Two patients of the monopolar group in the study done by T.Jagadeeswar et al required a blood transfusion for the severe drop in he- myoglobin.[8] Marco de Sio et al and Henry S.S. Ho et al found no significant difference in change in serum hemoglobin, between two groups in their study.[5,10]

In our study, the change in serum sodium concentration was significantly greater in the monopolar group compared to the bipolar group both immediate and 24 hours postoperatively. The change in serum sodium values from pre-op to immediate postoperatively was significantly more

in the monopolar group (4.13 \pm 1.14) compared to the bipolar group (0.83 \pm 0.89) with a p value<0.001. Also, the change in serum sodium values from pre-op to 24 hours postoperatively was significantly more in the monopolar group (3.74 \pm 1.18) compared to the bipolar group (0.96 \pm 1.12) with a p value<0.001. The lowest serum sodium levels postoperatively were 132 mEq/L immediate postoperatively and 133 mEq/L 24 hours postoperatively. A significant change in serum sodium levels from preoperative to postoperative values in the monopolar group more than the bipolar group were also found in studies done by T. Jagadeeswar et al, Henry S.S. Ho et al and Mohamed Hafez El Saied Hafez et al.[8,10,14] Piyush Singhanian et al showed a greater decline in serum sodium in the monopolar group in their study but it was not statistically significant[16]. While Marco de Sio et al, Erturhan et al found no significant difference in change in serum sodium between two groups in their study. [5,11]

Changes in serum potassium levels have also been studied in TURP. Norlen et al. reported dilution hypokalemia when distilled water was used as an irrigant [17] In contrast, Krishna Moorthy et al. reported significant hyperkalemia in patients undergoing TURP and percutaneous nephrostolithotomy with glycine and sterile water as the irrigant, probably due to hemolysis during fluid absorption into the circulation. Although, there was no alteration in potassium levels when normal saline was used as the irrigant [18] Hyperkalemic cardiotoxicity is increased by hyponatremia and acidosis. It is possible that the cardiovascular changes occurring in TURP syndrome can be a combination of both hyponatremia and acidosis. Henry S.S. Ho et al found no significant difference in change in serum hemoglobin, between two groups in their study.[10]

In our study, no significant changes in potassium levels were observed in either of the groups.

A positive correlation has been found between the duration of surgery and change in hemoglobin and serum sodium levels both immediate and 24 hours postoperatively. With increasing duration of surgery, the amount of irrigation fluid getting absorbed into systemic circulation increases and thus increases the risk of TUR syndrome. Prolonged resection times also expose the open prostatic sinuses for a longer time and can contribute to the increased amount of blood loss during the surgery.

In the monopolar group, catheter removal was done within 24 hours postoperatively in 86.95% and in bipolar group, it was 95.65%. It was comparable in both the groups with a p-value of 0.6077.

Although there was a significant change in serum sodium levels postoperatively in the monopolar

group, no case of TUR syndrome was reported. T. Jagadeeswar et al and Mohamed Hafez El Saied Hafez et al had reported 1 case, Erturhan et al, Ho et al recorded 2 cases of TUR syndrome in the monopolar group. [8,14,11] While Yousef et al reported 17 cases of TUR syndrome in the monopolar group. The higher incidence of TUR syndrome found in the study by Yousef et al can be probably due to learning curve effects, resection of the large size of the prostate or different hospital protocols.[19]

One patient in the monopolar group had postoperative bleeding but didn't require blood transfusion. No other known complications of TURP were reported in either of the groups. Erturhan et al have reported urethral injury and meatal strictures in Bipolar TURP group more frequent than the monopolar group.[11] The study done by T. Jagadeeswar et al showed no postoperative urethral strictures in the bipolar group whereas 2 patients in the monopolar group had strictures which required intervention.[8]

The complication rate observed in our study was less probably because of small sample size, the inclusion of only ASA 1 & 2 patients in the study, increasing skill and experience of the surgeon with the procedure, limited resection time, more awareness and vigilance of the surgeon and the anaesthetist about risks and possible complications of TURP. A larger number of study subjects and a longer period of follow up is required to conclude the reduced complication rates and better safety profile of bipolar TURP over monopolar TURP.

Limitation of our study

It was an observational study with a sample size of 46 patients. It was a single center study.

Conclusion

Bipolar TURP is better in terms of change in serum sodium and hemoglobin levels both immediate and 24 hours postoperatively, which was significantly more in the monopolar group. No case of TUR syndrome was recorded in our study. The duration of surgery and amount of irrigation fluid used was significantly lesser in the bipolar group. A positive correlation is found between duration of surgery and change in serum sodium and hemoglobin levels both immediate and 24 hours postoperatively. The duration of anesthesia, weight of the resected prostate gland and number of patients with catheter removed within 24 hours postoperatively was comparable in both the groups. From our study, we conclude that Bipolar TURP is better in terms of safety and complication rates compared to monopolar TURP.

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